

Influence of Solvent Composition on the Rates of Basic Hydrolysis of Cinnamic Esters

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The effect of dielectric character of a solvent on the basic hydrolysis of ethyl cinnamate, methyl cinnamate was studied in various mixed solvents like ethanol-water and acetone-water mixtures. The results have been discussed in the light of Laidler-Landskroener expression. Linear relationship was found between the rate constant and Grunwald-Winstein 'Y' values of the solvent compositions.

The present paper reports the data on the influence of dielectric constant on rate constant of this reaction. It is well known that the property of the solvent is closely connected with the polarity of the solvent i.e., the dielectric constant. Many equations have been derived to correlate the dielectric constant with the reaction velocity. Earliest of them was that of Laidler and Eyring¹ who gave the following equation for the reaction between ions and neutral molecules.

For the bimolecular reaction, $A+B \rightleftharpoons M^{\ddagger}$ products, the equation for the specific rate constant k

$$\begin{aligned}
 Ink = Ink_0 + \frac{\xi Z_A^2}{2kT} (1/D-1) (1/R_A - 1/R_M) - 1/kT \frac{\mu B^2}{r^2 B} \frac{(D_0-1)}{(2D_0+1)} + \left[b_A - b_M \frac{\xi \delta}{DrkT} \right] \cdot \mu \\
 + \frac{\phi_A + \phi_B - \phi_M}{kT} \quad \dots (1)
 \end{aligned}$$

Laidler and Landskroener² used Kirkwood's³ and Kirkwood-Westheimer's⁴ equation to develop the following general equation incorporating the corrections due to non-electrostatic forces.

$$\begin{aligned}
 Ink = Ink_0 + \frac{\xi^2}{2kT} (1/D-1) \left[\frac{Z_A^2}{b_A} + \frac{Z_B^2}{b_B} - \frac{(Z_A + Z_B)^2}{b^{\ddagger}} \right] \\
 \frac{3\xi^2}{8kT} \left(\frac{2}{D} - 1 \right) \left[\frac{G_A}{b^3_A} + \frac{G_B}{b^3_B} - \frac{G^{\ddagger}}{b^{\ddagger 3}} \right] \quad \dots (2)
 \end{aligned}$$

Here k_0 is the rate constant in very dilute solution, μ and r are the dipole moment and the molecular radius. If the non-electrostatic forces are small in comparison with other, ϕ may be neglected as a first approximation; it is then apparent that plot of $\log k$ against reciprocal of the dielectric constant, will be linear.

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2. K. J. Laidler and P. A. Landskroener, *Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1956, **52**, 200.
3. J. G. Kirkwood, *J. Chem. Phys.*, 1934, **2**, 351.
4. J. G. Kirkwood and F. H. Westheimer, *J. Chem. Phys.*, 1938, **6**, 506.

According to equation (2), a plot of $\log k$ versus $1/D$ should yield a straight line of slope given by the expression

$$S = \frac{\xi^2}{2.303 (2 kT)} \left[\frac{Z_A^2}{b_A} + \frac{Z_B^2}{b_B} - \frac{(Z_A + Z_B)^2}{b^{\ddagger}} + \frac{3}{2} \left(\frac{G_A}{b_A^3} + \frac{G_B}{b_B^3} - \frac{G_X}{b^{\ddagger 3}} \right) \right] \quad \dots (3)$$

For a uniunivalent ion reacting with a dipolar molecule $Z_A = \pm 1$, $Z_B = 0$, $Z_A^2 = +1$, $Z_B = 0$, $G_A = 0$ and G_B is negligible. Under these circumstances equation (3) becomes

$$S = \frac{\xi^2}{2.303 (2 kT)} \left[\frac{1}{b_A} - \frac{1}{b^{\ddagger}} - \frac{3}{2} \frac{G_X}{b^{\ddagger 3}} \right] \quad \dots (4)$$

In order to evaluate b^{\ddagger} Landskroener and Laidler (loc. cit.) constructed a model for the basic hydrolysis of ester from which G_X and b_A values were evaluated

To test the above theory $\log k$ values were plotted against $1/D$ for the alkaline hydrolysis of cinnamic esters in ethanol-water and acetone-water mixtures. The values of dielectric constant at the compositions and temperatures for the study are those of Akarlof⁵. The slopes of the straight lines obtained were used to calculate b^{\ddagger} from equation (3). The values are given in Table III. The values of b^{\ddagger} were found to be of the magnitude of a molecular dimension confirming the theory with experimental

The reaction rates have been found to be faster in acetone-water mixtures than in methanol-water mixture. The rate constant increases with the increase in dielectric constant within the same solvent mixtures

The values of $\log k$ with $1/D$ vary linearly with both ethanol and methanol water mixtures with negative slopes. This fact contradicts the prediction of the equation of Laidler and Eyring (loc. cit.) and Amis and Jaffe⁶. These deviations with the sign of the slope may be attributed as the non-electrostatic interacting forces which are considerable at high concentration of water.

The variations of $\log k$ with $1/D$ for acetone-water mixtures is in agreement with the predictions of Laidler and Landskroener (loc. cit.). This increase in rate constant with increase in dielectric constant can be ascribed to the formation of activated complex more polar than the reactants. Similar observations were made by Parausanu⁷ for acid hydrolysis of butyl acetate in acetone-water solution

The activation energy and hence the rate constant is found to be linearly related to the mole fraction of water in the solvent mixture. It is a well known fact that in ester hydrolysis solvation will be preferentially greater for the transition state than for the reactants. The increase of rate constant due to the greater preferential solvation of the transition state results in the decrease of activation energy. The activation energy decreases considerably from 90% to 50% in both alcohol and acetone.

5. G. J. Akarlof, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1932, **54**, 7125.

6. E. S. Amis and G. Jaffe, *J. Chem. Phys.*, 1942, **10**, 598.

7. V. Parausanu, *Chem. Abstr.*, 1962, **56**, 66959.

It is quite surprising that in case of ethyl cinnamate there is a change in the nature of the graph around 30% water (ethanol : water—70 : 30) at all the temperatures. This may be due to the greater solvation of the transition state with increase in water content in the reaction mixture. This type of behaviour for the solvent composition has also been noted by Hudson⁸ and Cropper⁹.

The various properties which contribute to the ability of a solvent to solvate ions can be measured by the quantity 'Y' termed as the ionising power of the solvent^{10,11} which is a function of solvent solute interaction defined by the equation¹¹

$$\log k = \log k_0 + mY.$$

In the current case 'Y' function has provided a close description of rate variation^{10,11}. The value of 'Y' were taken from the work of Winstein and coworkers^{10,11}. Straight line plots between $\log k$ and Y values were obtained for ethanol-water and acetone-water mixtures.

Recently¹² the Z-values of Kosower¹³, based on charge transfer spectra of pyridinium iodides, are being used for measure of solvent polarity. The $\log k$ values for ethanol-water, acetone-water were plotted against Kosower's Z values. Excellent plots were obtained in each case.

Comparison of the rate-of methyl and ethyl cinnamate : In the alkaline hydrolysis of esters, the reaction site is trigonal in the reactant state and tetrahedral in the transition state^{14,15}. Consequently steric factor will be greater in the transition state than in the less crowded reactant state¹⁵. This will lead to the increase of energy of activation and decrease of rate constant. Because of the interposition of oxygen atom between the carbonyl carbon and R¹ (R-CH = CH-COOR¹) the polar effects are shielded to the reaction site¹⁵. Since the ethyl group is more bulkier than the methyl group, the value of energy of activation is more in the former case than in the latter.

EXPERIMENTAL

Ethyl cinnamate and methyl cinnamate were repeatedly fractionally distilled under reduced pressure and the middle fraction was collected

Ethyl alcohol was purified according to the method of Rout *et al.*¹⁶

Acetone and methanol used are of analar quality. The method of rate measurement and the calculation of rate constant were similar as described by Watson¹⁷. The values of

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10. A. H. Fainberg and S. Winstein, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1957, **79**, 1957; 1602, 1608.
11. S. G. Smith, A. H. Fainberg and S. Winstein, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1961, **83**, 618.
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16. P. L. Nayak and M. K. Rout. Kinetics of base catalysed condensation of acetophenone with benzaldehydes (in Press).
17. W. Watson, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1937, 1430.

the rate constant together with the parameters of the transition state theory are described in Table I, II and III.

TABLE I

Values of the specific reaction rate for hydrolysis of ethyl cinnamate in ethanol-water mixture

Ethanol V/V	%	$k \times 10^3 \text{ lit mole}^{-1} \text{ sec}^{-1}$				E K. Cal/mole	ΔF^\ddagger K. Cal	$-\Delta S^\ddagger$ Cals/deg.
		k_{25}	k_{30}	k_{35}	k_{40}			
EtOH	90	0.83	2.08	3.1	5.4	24.50	23.40	19.42
EtOH	85	1.39	2.25	3.6	6.5	22.40	23.20	26.53
EtOH	70	5.50	10.0	15.5	—	19.70	22.50	30.08
EtOH	60	6.90	12.3	18.3	—	18.40	22.40	32.02
EtOH	50	10.0	13.3	20.01	—	14.40	22.30	35.32

TABLE II

Values of specific reaction rate of hydrolysis of methyl cinnamate in ethanol-water mixture

Ethanol	%	$k \times 10^3 \text{ lit mole}^{-1} \text{ sec}^{-1}$			E K. Cals/mole	ΔF^\ddagger K. Cal	$-\Delta S^\ddagger$ Cals/deg.
		25	30	40			
EtOH	90	1.77	2.20	4.50	11.50	22.00	34.65
EtOH	85	2.08	3.75	5.00	11.00	21.70	35.19
EtOH	80	3.06	6.90	10.01	10.60	21.30	35.52
EtOH	70	5.80	9.10	13.30	9.70	21.20	37.92

TABLE III

Values of specific reaction rate and parameters of transition state theory for hydrolysis of ethyl cinnamate in acetone-water mixture

Acetone V/V %	$k \times 10^3 \text{ in litre mole}^{-1} \text{ sec}^{-1}$			E K. Cal/mole	ΔF^\ddagger K. Cal	$-\Delta S^\ddagger$ Cal/deg.
	25	30	35			
90	1.08	2.66	4.33	22.10	21.80	2.24
80	2.66	5.50	7.50	20.70	21.40	2.29
70	10.00	15.60	27.70	18.40	20.80	8.02
60	19.04	25.50	32.30	11.50	20.50	29.84

TABLE IV

Values of the parameter $b \pm$ in case of the basic hydrolysis of ethyl cinnamate

Name of the ester	Solvent	Temp. °C	Slope	$b \pm$
Ethyl cinnamate	Alcohol-water	25	0.96×10^2	3.00
Ethyl cinnamate	Alcohol-water	30	0.72×10^2	2.96
Ethyl cinnamate	Acetone-water	25	0.68×10^2	2.90
Ethyl cinnamate	Acetone-water	30	0.62×10^2	2.89